

TITLE

System and Method for Managing and Monitoring Customer Behavior

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Introduction:

Marketing means understanding and meeting the needs of consumers. To understand this, it is very important to understand the behavior of the consumer. Consumer behavior means behavior of the consumer that they show to fulfill their needs. Just like you need a smart phone to fulfill this need, the behavior you show is called consumer behavior. How do you search which smart phone you will buy? Where will you buy it? How to buy once purchased, how will you use it? If the phone is defective, how will you dispose it? Everything is a part of consumer behavior. It is very important for a company to understand a consumer.

For any company to become successful, it is must to know

- Why a consumer buys a goods or service?
- Where do he buy from?
- How do one buy?
- When do they buy?
- What do they buy?

If the company has the answers to these questions, then it can succeed very easily and can sell its product and service well. In fact every consumer is different like we are different from our brother, friend, sister, mother and father.

But there is one thing common amongst us and that is why every consumer buy and use a product and service, so it is very important for a marketer to understand how a consumer buys goods or services.

Buying behavior of Consumer

It refers to the buying behavior of the potential consumers that means individuals and households who buy goods and services for their personal use.

The main target of the marketers are that how consumers respond to various marketing strategies
...
any actually plan for the better marketing of the product and customers satisfaction?"

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Important aspect that affects consumer behavior

- Some personal aspect are age, gender, lifestyle and social environment.
- Consumer can take their own decision freely.
- Consumer's thinking order and choice.
- It can be influenced by family, friends, relatives and neighbors.
- Consumer must be well educated to understand the right choice for product.

Fig1. Model for customer behavior

Consumer behavior affects by personal aspect such as:

- Cultural aspect is something in which culture, social culture and social class is the main criteria.
- Social aspectsuch as in which community you live, which type of people live around you.
- Personal aspect such as your age, gender, life style, profession, occupation, personality and your thinking order and status of living.
- Psychological aspect which affects your psychology means how you think and behave for some product.

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Fig2. Some Aspect that influence consumer behavior

Cultural Aspect

- Culture is very important parameter for individual's choice.
- Subcultures includes group of people that shared common life experiences and situations.
- Social classes are constant and share similar values, interests and behaviors.

Social Aspect

Some social aspect that affects individual's thinking order are:

- Groups of consumers
- Family values that play significant role.
- Social roles like what type of profession you are having accordingly you buy particular product that suits to your society.
- Status that you have in which company your are working, what type of neighborhood you are having that always create impact on behavior.

Consumer Groups

- Persons attitude and behavior are affected by many criteria like small groups
high types of social groups they have.
membership groups like what type of members are there in group.

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Personal Aspect are as follow

- Age and gender because every product have a value for some person and not valuable for other like if customer is young their thinking will be different, they can spend more money on their choices not for need while aged people always fulfill their basic need not their interests.
- Occupation also plays important role because if you have nice salary you will definitely go for luxurious brands on the other hand if you have limited salary then you have to buy cheap items that suits to your pocket.
- Economic situation like what type of family you have, do they have enough money it shows their economic condition.
- Lifestyle shows how well you earn, can you earn branded stuffs or you buy things that your pocket allows.

Psychological Aspect are like

- Psychology is a thinking order of a person.
- It depends on where you born.
- Type of environment is there in your country.
- What occupation your mother and father are having.
- Which type of education you have.
- What moral values you are having

All these criteria affect the psychology of any person.

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Fig3. Individuals need

- Psychology always affects any individual's behavior and after getting experience it changes.

Fig4. Buyer decision process

Information retrieval

Information can be obtained from various sources:

- Personal Sources that we get from Family, friends and neighbors.
- Commercial Sources that can be gather from Advertising, sales people, displays, packaging and dealers.
- Public Sources like we can collect them from Restaurant reviews and editorials

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Mood of the customer after purchase

Customers satisfaction can only be getting through the lesser gap between their expectation and the product or service they get from company, only then one can get the higher sell on your product.

Conclusion

The proposed solution towards the problem of statements is stated and concluded that the marketers must try to understand consumer behavior in order to deliver greater consumer satisfaction. Understanding who and why individuals or groups buy products and services helps marketers design more attractive marketing programs.

If an organization can determine what satisfies customers, the organization can implement the concept of marketing and better predict how consumers will respond to different marketing programs.

References

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